

PRODUCTION OF SM₂S₃ AND SM₂O₂S BY THE SULFIDATION METHOD.

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ABSTRACT

Seldom earth elements dioxysulfides were Ln₂O₂S prepared in the following reaction sequence. Compounds Ln₂S₃ (Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd, Dy, Lu) were prepared by reacting seldom earth elements semitoric oxides with sulfiding gases H₂S –CS₂. Sulfidation was carried out at temperatures of 1050-1150oC. The sequence in Ln₂S₃ systems is Ln₂O₃ at synthesis temperatures. The reflection of the Sm₂O₂SO₄ compound is on the diffraction pattern. The diffraction pattern of the sample annealed at 700°C indicates an increased noise level. Phase change occurs when the Sm₂O₂SO₄ compound sample is treated at 700°C [7]. The sample will first be a two-phase Sm₂O₂SO₄ , Sm₂O₂S, then a single-phase Sm₂O₂S. As the temperature increases, the time to achieve a uniform state Sm₂O₂S decreases. The composition of the product is ambiguous and it is known that H₂S, CS₂, NH₃, S, guanide and melanin are formed as a result of the degradation of the thiocyanate. Treatment was carried out to obtain semitoric samarium sulfides Sm₂S₃ without impurity phases according to X-rays phase analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Seldom earth elements dioxysulfides were Ln₂O₂S prepared in the following reaction sequence. The seldom earth elements half-core oxides were dissolved in nitric acid, then a sulfate precipitate was obtained by sulfuric acid, the solutions were evaporated to dryness at 100-110°C, and the mixture was annealed at 700°C for 1 hour to remove nitrogen oxides and sulfur. By treating anhydrous Sm₂(SO₄)₃ in a hydrogen stream at 700°C, Sm₂O₂S were obtained which were further treated for 1 hour at 800° C in a H₂S stream [1]. Waterless

sulfates $Gd_2(SO_4)_3$, $Dy_2(SO_4)_3$, $Lu_2(SO_4)_3$ processed in H_2 stream 550-600°C within the 3rd hour in the beginning, and then in H_2S stream at 800-900°C within the 5th hour. Single-phase defects of Ln_2O_2S compounds [1] were obtained.

Compounds Ln_2S_3 ($Ln = Nd, Sm, Gd, Dy, Lu$) were prepared by reacting PEE semitoxic oxides with sulfiding gases $H_2S - CS_2$. Sulfidation was carried out at temperatures of 1050-1150°C. The sequence in Ln_2S_3 systems is Ln_2O_3 at synthesis temperatures [3].

Fig. Phase diagram system $Sm_2S_3 - Sm_2O_3$.

Purpose: Preparation of Sm_2S_3 and Sm_2O_2S by sulfidic method.

EXPERIMENT TECHNIQUES

The samples were studied by X-ray (RFA) (diffractometer ДРОН-6, CoKa radiation Fe filter), visual poly thermal (VPTA), microstructural (MSA) (Microstructural analysis was performed on a metallographic microscope AxioVert .A1MAT manufactured by ZEISS (Germany), resolution 0.5 μm . The image from the microscope was transmitted to a computer through a video camera. Software complex AxioVision SE64) analysis was used for obtaining photos of grain sizing. Cell parameters are calculated using the High Score Plus program (data collection for the Drone-6 set; diffrac.file exchange. V5) with accuracy ± 0.001 and ± 0.0001 nm for rhombic and cubic structures, respectively. Mathematical processing of data of thermal methods of research and graphical constructions are performed in the program Edstate 2D. Evaluation of melting heat was carried out according to Van Laar equation [5].

RESULTS AND THEIR DISCUSSION

Synthesis of Sm_2O_2S . Literary data on structure and properties of Sm_2O_2S compounds are given. Available data on deformation in upstream direction, kinetic properties of process during processing of REM sulphates in hydrogen flow, sulfide gases, phase diagrams of $Sm_2S_3 - Sm_2O_3$ systems, kinetics of heterogeneous reactions and kinetics of formation of lanthanide oxysulfide are summarized. Equipment for thermal treatment of materials in hydrogen flow consists of electric heating furnace with hydrogen generator, hydrogen supply source and

device for control of power supplied to furnace. The treated material was placed in a reactor consisting of an outer quartz tube with a sealed bottom. The reactor has a gas outlet, an inner quartz glass, and a quartz gas supply tube. The flow of hydrogen fed through the tube must react evenly with all quartz glass materials. The treatment of the $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4$ in the hydrogen stream at 700°C (300 minutes or less) did not change the phase state of the material. The reflection of the $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4$ compound is on the diffraction pattern. The diffraction pattern of the sample annealed at 700°C indicates an increased noise level. Phase change occurs when the $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4$ compound sample is treated at 700°C [7]. The sample will first be a two-phase $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_2\text{SO}_4$, $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$, then a single-phase $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$. As the temperature increases, the time to achieve a uniform state $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ decreases.

This line limits the homogeneity of the $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ phase.

$\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$ target phase in it was more than 100% according to the results of X-rays phase analysis.

Fig. 1. The diffractogram of the sample $\text{Sm}_2\text{O}_2\text{S}$, after synthesis in a H_2 stream at 700°C , hexagonal singonium P-3ml, $a = 3.8889$, $c = 6.7221$ (Å). Survey conditions: $\text{Cu K}\alpha$, Ni filter.

Synthesis of Sm_2S_3 in a stream of sulfiding agents. For the synthesis of semitoric samarium sulfides in the sulfide stream, the procedure described in [6] was $\text{H}_2\text{S} - \text{CS}_2$ used. The plant includes the following parts: two electric furnaces and two quartz reactors with heating control, for synthesis of sulfiding agents, two for phase synthesis. Temperature control in the furnace was carried out using chromoaluminium thermocouples. The synthesis used a vertical reactor in which the gas passed through the treated material and the reaction gas product was removed from the reactor. Thus, maximum contact was achieved between the sulfided gas and the preform.

The sulfide gas was obtained by heat treatment of rhodium-ammonium in a quartz reactor at a decomposition temperature of 240°C . Thus, the gaseous decomposition products of ammonium rhodanide- NH_3 , H_2S , CS_2 with argon flow are transferred to the phase synthesis reactor and remain in the rhodanide reactor. Water-soluble precipitate with low volatility.

In sulfidation, the most important decomposition products are carbon disulfide CS_2 and hydrogen sulfide H_2S . Crystalline ammonium sulfide is formed in the cold upper part of the reactor and tube, which is formed by the reaction of ammonia and hydrogen sulfide. Argon is fed to the sulfide gas flow control system. Argon feed rate is 0.5-1.0 ml/s. The thiocyanate decomposition reaction is very complex. The composition of the product is ambiguous and it is known that H_2S , CS_2 , NH_3 , S, guanide and melanin are formed as a result of the degradation

of the thiocyanate.

The synthesis temperature may vary from room temperature to 1227°C. The lower temperature limit is set by the temperature interaction of the sulphide gas and the workpiece, the performance of the upper electric furnace, and the working temperature of the quartz[13].

For the synthesis of one and half of samarium sulfide Sm_2S_3 samarium oxide Sm_2O_3 was used, which was previously obtained by decomposition of 5 chemically samarium nitrate $\text{Sm}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ "chemically pure" variety.

The Sm_2O_3 oxide was placed in a quartz reactor for the synthesis of sulfide phases. The sulfide gas was passed through the oxide layer at a temperature of 1150-1200°C. The synthesis time was on average about 20-25 hours[11]. Treatment was carried out to obtain semitoxic samarium sulfides Sm_2S_3 without impurity phases according to X-rays phase analysis.

The reaction equation for producing Sm_2S_3 from Sm_2O_3 in a stream of sulfiding agents ($\Delta G_{\text{GS}_2}^0 = 65, 91 \text{ kJ/mol}$, $\Delta G_{\text{H}_2\text{S}}^0 = -33.81 \text{ kJ/mol}$. CS_2 is the main sulfiding gas) [6].

Fig. 2. Diffractogram of low-temperature modification of $\alpha\text{-Sm}_2\text{S}_3$. Rhombic singonium Pnma, $a = 7,38260$, $b = 3,97514$ $c = 15,3781$ (Å). Survey conditions: $\text{CuK}\alpha$, Ni filter.

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